

Assessment of Digital Technology Affordances and Epistemological Access in Higher Educational Institutions of Learning in Nigeria: a Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

This paper was aimed at assessing the digital technology affordances and epistemological access in higher educational institutions in Nigeria as a system literature review. The authors used a concept-centric systematic literature review approach to conduct their study. Following the development of a research protocol, the authors searched the information systems database and other relevant and pertinent databases to select relevant articles for review. A thematic coding approach consists of six steps: (1) familiarizing with the data; (2) generating initial codes; (3) creation of themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) defining and labeling themes; and (6) producing the report. The systematic literature review revealed several themes (for example, educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities) that are critical to digital technological affordances and epistemological access. Thus, from this review, the authors developed a framework that harmonizes various concepts that characterize epistemological access in higher educational institutions. The synthesized theoretical framework offers an integrated perspective on how structural and cultural systems of students and digital technology can facilitate the assessment of digital technologies and epistemological access in higher educational institutions in Nigeria. Moreover, it addresses gaps such as the influence of e-learning management systems on faculties during dialogic interaction, where a framework was developed. The framework not only provides new research avenues in the information systems domain but also serves as inspiration for future empirical testing in higher educational institutions globally. It is therefore recommended that, universities in Nigeria should integrate digital learning platform, enhance usability through user-centric design, maximize affordances of digital technologies, implement transformative educational strategies, and address structural barriers.

Keyword: Epistemological access, affordances, digital technologies, higher educational institutions

Introduction

As digital technologies are developing, technology-integrated learning has also evolved, and the demand for technology in education has increased (Ma et al., 2020). Digital technology affordances have entered a new phase with the introduction of new modern technologies in the education context, for example learning management systems, digital libraries, open ERP, Sakai. The affordances of digital technologies have given rise to extraordinary and diversified digital innovations, which should assist in dialogical interaction via digital supportive classrooms in higher education institutions. Digital technologies provide convenience for learning among students and context awareness (Tan-Hsu et al., 2012), ease knowledge delivery by teachers (Cheikh-Ammar, 2018), improve communicative skills and competence (Liaw, 2014), and promote learning autonomy (Baran & AlZoubi, 2020; Ma et al., 2020). Therefore, digital technology affordances have been identified as a new concept that has important future directions (Al-Maawali, 2020; Bahari, 2021; Bobsin et al., 2019; Eshchar-Netz & Vedder-Weiss, 2021; K. Lee et al., 2014) for gaining access to education in higher education institutions, especially even among less privileged students.

Despite the promising and important future of digital technology affordances, the successful integration of digital technologies into higher education institutions requires the full engagement and dedication of educators and policymakers (D'Ambra *et al.*, 2019). But research has shown that faculties in higher educational institutions in sub-Saharan Africa are often hesitant or even refuse to use digital technologies as a way for students to get an education (Ma *et al.*, 2020). With the introduction of high-tech learning environments, such as flipped learning (Sams & Bergmann, 2013), massive open online courses (MOOCs) (Siemens, 2012), mobile technology, and social media, the use of digital technologies for gaining access to education in higher educational institutions (HEIs) in most African countries, specifically Nigeria, is highly critical. As these learning contexts could greatly facilitate and ease access to education when deployed, higher educational institutions in Nigeria have not embraced digital technologies (Okwelogu *et al.*, 2021), even though the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education and the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Digital Economy have been encouraging staff of higher educational institutions to use cutting-edge technologies effectively for teaching and learning purposes, with the hope of bridging the gap between marginalized groups and the elites' children in rural and urban regions (Adamu, 2019; Okwelogu *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, the majority of university lecturers in Nigeria are not using the available digital technologies even if they are provided for teaching as envisioned by the Federal Ministry of Education (Okwelogu *et al.*, 2021). They either responded poorly to facilities provided (Huang *et al.*, 2021; Ma *et al.*, 2020), or used them in ways that lacked innovation and creativity (Li, 2017). Okwelogu *et al.* (2021) in their study asserted that inadequate funding, fall in national review, insecurity, corruption, inadequate ICT expertise, shortage of infrastructural facilities, political instability, and policy instability were among the problems hindering effective use of technologies for teaching and learning. Therefore, there is also a severe gap between policy requirements and teaching practice (Adamu, 2019; Kuru Gönen, 2019; Luo *et al.*, 2021; Okwelogu *et al.*, 2021) when it comes to technology usage in classrooms. Barriers like insufficient access to an appropriate learning management system, insufficiency in teachers' technology competence and confidence (Liaw, 2014), the influence of Confucianism that emphasizes respecting authority (Fu *et al.*, 2020), prioritizes academic performance, and accentuates the role of examinations (Kuru Gönen, 2019), have frequently been mentioned in literature concerning the implementation of ICT-based for teaching and learning in higher educational institutions. In most literature (Al-Ani, 2013; Al-Maawali, 2020; Antonenko *et al.*, 2017; Bahari, 2021; Bray & Tangney, 2016; Dinsmore, 2019; Eshchar-Netz & Vedder-Weiss, 2021; Gibson *et al.*, 2021; Kuru Gönen, 2019; Okwelogu *et al.*, 2021; Wankel & Blessinger, 2013), studies are mainly conducted in relation to ICT facilities for teaching and learning. There is a dearth of studies regarding access to right/disciplinary knowledge in universities (Okwelogu *et al.*, 2021), especially through digitally supported classroom dialogue. In other words, an up-to-date systematic literature review with a focus on underprivileged students or marginalized groups for social inclusion in HEIs is still lacking. Moreover, affordance has not been actualized within the context of epistemological access and social justice. Hence, we are looking at epistemological access as social justice. In this study, we hope to use the educational affordances of digital technologies to facilitate epistemological access, thereby achieving social justice for underprivileged students or marginalized groups/students from rural communities or areas. Marginalized groups in this study are referred to as those students who do not have the upbringing that is supposed to support their educational career. Thus, we pose the following research question:

Research Question 1: How are the educational affordances of digital technologies for gaining epistemological access among marginalized groups contextualized in higher institutions in sub-Saharan African universities?

Research Question 2: What challenges may implicate gaining epistemological access in a quest to use digital technologies for dialogic interaction in higher institutions in sub-Saharan Africa?

To address such a research gap and answer the posed research questions, we adopt a systematic literature review approach which is rigorous and transparent (Okoli & Schabram, 2010; Schryen, 2015; Schryen *et al.*, 2017), by reviewing 10 years of literature (2012-2022) on Digital Technology Affordances in Context for Epistemological Access with a systematic analysis of the trending issues, and research methodologies and theories over one decade. This method is the most reliable and comprehensive about what works.

Methodology

Literature Identification

The literature search was based on the aim and scope of the review. As noted by IS scholars (for example, Baghizadeh *et al.*, 2020; Bai *et al.*, 2019; Bandara *et al.*, 2015; Ferreras-Fernández *et al.*, 2016; Schryen *et al.*, 2017; Watson & Webster, 2020) to review a specific subject area, a review article should be able to (1) survey and synthesize previous studies; (2) identify the

relationships between key concepts; (3) identify gaps; and (4) set directions for future research. To do this, systematic literature review process and protocol was developed as shown in **Figure 1**. A protocol based on Levy and Ellis (2006); Bandara et al. (2015); and Boell and Wang (2019) was further developed, with the goal of focusing on the need for research in perception. At first, we started by identifying various service sources in which the literature was searched. These sources comprise the renowned information systems (IS) databases, journals, and conferences in the IS domain. We searched databases (e.g., Google scholar and other pertinent databases such as AISEL, JStore, Springer, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Elsevier) that house vital academic IS journals (Lowry et al., 2013; Schryen, 2015; Schryen et al., 2017). Such journals were referred to as a set of top IS journals (Boell & Wang, 2019; Lowry et al., 2013). Moreover, we leverage service from the association of information systems for electronic library (AISEL) in order to capture recent studies from reputable conference proceedings such as the AMCIS, PACIS, IFIP, and other relevant information systems conferences, and Literature Baskets (www.litbasket.io) (Boell & Wang, 2019). Moreover, educational information systems journals were also searched as the most frequently used databases, especially in information systems studies (Ajah & Ononiwu, 2021; Boell & Wang, 2019; Inuwa et al., 2020; Lowry et al., 2013).

Second, the search terms in the process include: (Affordances) OR (Information Systems Affordance) OR (Information Technology Affordance) OR (Information Communication Technology Affordance) OR (Digital Affordance) OR (Technology Affordance) OR (E-learning Affordance) OR (Online Learning Affordance) OR (Mobile Learning Affordance) OR (Mobile Learning Affordance) OR (Learning Management System Affordance) OR (Educational Technology Affordance). Preliminary relevance was determined for each manuscript title. From the title, if the content seemed to discuss any of the search keywords, we obtained its full reference, including author, year, title, and abstract, for further evaluation. Despite the technological advancement and the methods of information archiving and retrieval, we searched for studies that were published between 2012-2022 (articles published for one decade), so that we could build our review on the recent literatures considering information retrieval and synthesis in the digital age. In all, 332 studies that matched the search keywords were found across the searched journals and conferences, and they were all moved to EndNote library TH20 in order to ascertain whether the studies should be included or not. Although, the search has covered the pertinent academic IS journals (Lowry et al., 2013; Merriam, 2015), we can argue that such a literature search was comprehensive enough to capture the most recent and relevant studies for the review.

In the last stage of the protocol (i.e., **3rd Phase: Output; Figure 1**), the writing of the literature kick-start through answering the research questions set for the study as well as setting future direction. To answer the research questions in this study, all the obtained articles were screened using inclusion and exclusion criteria based on certain procedures. These processes are described in the following sections.

Screening for Inclusion and Exclusion Procedures

It appeared that 321 studies were obtained as a result of the search terms, and the papers were archived in EndNote library TH20. Each of the 321 studies was analyzed to ascertain whether it conformed to the aim of the study as well as the inclusion and exclusion criteria. These inclusion and exclusion criteria are: (1) Does the study clearly define concepts and the relationship among such concepts? (2) Are there specifications of concepts moderating the relationships amongst concepts? If not, can we use the moderators to infer concepts in operations by the researchers? (3) Is the study guided by a theory or theories to identify concepts? (4) Papers must be written in English. (5) A clear methodology and findings must be included, and (6) Are conceptual papers related to the phenomenon in question? We first read the abstracts of the 321 studies to further decide their relevance to the phenomenon under study, “Digital Technology Affordance for Epistemological Access,” and we found that 58 studies were deemed relevant, and we obtained the full-text article for quality assessment.

We further skimmed through the full-text articles to further evaluate the quality and eligibility of the studies. We deemed journal articles, conference papers, and books published by reputable publishers as high-quality research and, therefore, included in the review. Most of the anecdotal and technical reports as well as online presentations are excluded from the review because of the lack of a peer-review process.

Snowballing

We identified eleven (11) additional studies through backward and forward searching. We also utilized the forward and backward search to identify different affordance-related issues in higher education institutions. Once the article established affordance, or digital technology affordance, we identified best-practice examples by searching articles that had referenced the information systems paper. Examples were chosen based on their adherence to the method, after which preference was given to educationally related articles. Overall, 69 studies were included in this review, as shown in the second phase of **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Systematic Literature Review Process

A concept-centric approach (Webster & Watson, 2002) was used in this study to extract theoretical concepts from each of the 69 studies, which were further arranged as concept matrixes of digital technology affordance for epistemological access, as shown in **Table 1**. Moreover, concepts that are similar, which have sometimes had different semantic senses but with commensurable functional meanings from different studies, were merged as one concept (Templier & Pare, 2018) and placed in **Table 1**.

Overarching theme	Major themes	Second order themes (sub-theme)	First order concepts	Authors
Epistemological Access	Educational Technological Affordances	Usability, selection, browsing, representation of content, structuring collaborative learning process, provisionality, informing teachers, monitoring and regulation, engaging in co-construction, engaging in productive process, support/challenge, and assistive memory control	Accessibility, actualization, assessment, adoption, engagement, and perception.	(Bahari & Gholami, 2022; Bray & Tangney, 2016; Fromm et al., 2020; Paul M. Leonardi, 2013; Mascheroni & Vincent, 2016; Sethi, 2017; Thapa & Hatakka, 2017; Xiangming & Song, 2018; Zhao et al., 2021)
			Content creation, ease of use, ease of assimilation, evaluation, integration, internet provision, management, & monitoring.	(Ahad et al., 2018; Chatterjee et al., 2021; Cheikh-Ammar, 2018; Goldkuhl, 2020; Jais et al., 2021; Jónasdóttir & Müller, 2020; Nur'Aini, 2021; Strong et al., 2014; Tagoe & Cole, 2020; Turugare & Rudhumbu, 2020; Vonderwell & Zachariah, 2005; Q. Wang et al., 2013)
	Learning Context	Learner autonomy, learner inclusion and participation, classroom atmosphere, motivation & engagement, and interpersonal relationships	Awareness, influence, motivation, and performance.	(Al-Ani, 2013; Asamoah & Andoh-Baidoo, 2018; Asamoah, 2020; Jais et al., 2021; Lai, 2017; Payton & Kvasny, 2016)
			Contextual mobility, and material construction.	(Dinsmore, 2019)

	Dialogic Activities	Knowledge co-construction, using dialogue to express meta-cognitive learning, using dialogue to scaffold understanding between learner-learner & teacher-learner.	Association, accountability, archiving, autonomy, collaboration, communication, coordination, decoupling, desire to learn, editability, efficacy, expression, experience, interaction, intention, and presentation.	(Al-Ani, 2013; Asamoah, 2020; Bobsin et al., 2019; Chatterjee et al., 2021; Cordes, 2016; Dinsmore, 2019; Evans et al., 2017; Faik et al., 2020; Fu et al., 2019; Gillen & Kucirkova, 2018; Goldkuhl, 2020; Järvelä et al., 2015; Manca & Ranieri, 2013; Mao, 2014; McKenna, 2020; Rahimi et al., 2015; Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2020; Sethi, 2017; Strong et al., 2014; Tagoe & Cole, 2020; Waizenegger et al., 2020; C.-H. Wang et al., 2013; Wendt et al., 2022; Wyche & Steinfield, 2016; Young & Cleveland, 2022)
Table 1: Concepts Extraction from the Synthesized Studies				

As an iterative review process, we stopped harvesting more papers when saturation was reached, after careful and thorough reading of the papers (Cecez-Kecmanovic et al., 2014). We manually used a data extraction approach meant to store the data, followed by a thematic coding process (Leidner & Kayworth, 2006; Roberts et al., 2012; Wiener et al., 2016). “Such a coding procedure categorizes text information in a systematic manner and identifies relationships among the categories...” It’s useful for making sense of a big domain of research, and it can help direct future study (Roberts et al., 2012, p. 634). Following Braun and Clarke (2006), our thematic coding approach consists of six steps: (1) familiarizing with the data; (2) generating initial codes; (3) creation of themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) defining and labeling themes; and (6) producing the report. Starting with stage 1, we will go over the six steps in a way that mirrors how we used and adapted them for our data analysis.

First Stage: Familiarizing with the Data

The authors read and re-read each of the 69 studies that were identified and selected for inclusion in an active way (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This was to get more familiar with the selected studies and further clarify any discrepancies that might have occurred during the selection procedures. Thus, meanings and patterns were identified from the studies (Sinkovics, 2018).

Second Stage: Generating Initial Codes

The authors of this study independently identified the concepts, as QSR NVivo codes from empirical studies with theoretical underpinnings, while for the conceptual papers, only key concepts and phrases were considered. When such similar concepts from different studies were seen to have the same functional meaning, we merged them into one concept (Templier & Pare, 2018). The aggregate of the concepts now forms the first order concepts (Gioia et al., 2013; Sinkovics, 2018) or basic codes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A consensus was reached after comparing the codes found by the authors, and through mutual agreement, all the discrepancies were resolved, in which the first order categories emerged as shown in **Figure 2**. Ravasi and Phillips (2011) stated that the second stage is what made us switch from temporary to more permanent categories.

Figure 2: Thematic Data Analysis Process (Concept Mapping)

Third Stage: Development of Themes

Conceptual relations emerged among the emerging categories while grouping the codes that were kept close to the sliced-out concepts from the research evaluated, which were sorted into first-order categories. As a result, we merged first-order categories into fewer, larger, and potentially more relevant second-order categories (Ravasi & Phillips, 2011). The second-order categories suggest paying particular attention to them in order to solve the study’s overarching research questions. We carefully evaluated our first-order categories and their content across the 69 papers as the process progressed, looking for concepts that would – or would not – fit with each emerging category. We agreed to reframe or redefine some ideas when we realized that they had different meanings but were still basically the same (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Gioia et al., 2013).

Fourth Stage: Review of Themes

We thoroughly ran through the full data set for contradictory findings, then continued developing our second-order theme until saturation is reached by engaging in constant comparison (Belgrave & Seide, 2019; Braun & Clarke, 2006). Here, a thought or a phrase is compared to all prior concepts or phrases, rather than being analyzed on its own. We realized that the constant comparison process yielded theoretical attributes of second-order categories (Belgrave & Seide, 2019). As a result, we began to notice the extent of the categories, the variables that influenced them, the relationship between them, and the categories’ antecedents and effects (Belgrave & Seide, 2019).

The Fifth Stage: Defining and Naming Themes

Educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities were formed by combining second-order categories to establish three bigger encompassing themes. Furthermore, we saw how the three selected overarching themes cluster around a core subject (epistemological access), which is similar to Strauss and Corbin (1998) selective coding approach, as we noted in the memo. Similarly, we noticed that the categories were potentially saturated. **Figure 2** depicts the entire data structure that resulted from this procedure, including the first-order codes and their relations to the second-order categories and their relations, to the major themes, as well as the overarching theme that emerged.

Sixth Stage: Producing a Report

At this stage, the coded data and memos that can be used and worked with in this study have emerged. However, the final analysis and write-up of the report as detailed in the next section is presented.

Findings

In this study, descriptive statistics about the reviewed literature were provided as the first Phase. While the second Phase is a discussion of the main themes: Educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities as the major themes abstracted and synthesized from the literature review, as shown in **Table 1** for theoretical elaboration. The researchers consider the themes as critical for epistemological access. The descriptive statistics demonstrate the categories of articles, year of publication, methodology used, the countries of focus of selected studies, and specific databases. We commenced with descriptive statistics as detailed in the following section.

Descriptive Statistics

In this study, we reviewed 69 primary studies in relation to digital technology affordances in contexts for epistemological access; 50 of these studies were published as journal articles between 2016 and 2020. In 2012, only one study was published. Between 2021 and 2022, however, the number of articles published slowly declined, from 4 to 2, as shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Number selected journal paper each year

In terms of publication type, more than half (59 articles, i.e., 86%) of the reviewed articles were published as journal papers; 5 (7%) were published as conference papers; and 5 (7%) as books or book sections, as indicated in **Figure 4**.

S/No.	Types of publication	No. of Studies
1	Journal articles	59
2	Conference papers	5
3	Book/Book section	5
Total		69

Figure 4: Number of Articles by Type of Publication

With regards to the research method used, 30 (44%) of the studies used a qualitative technique as a method of data analysis, 17 (24.64%) used quantitative techniques such as descriptive statistics and regression analysis, 10 (14.50%) used both qualitative and quantitative techniques (i.e., mixed methods), 4 (5.8%) were papers that were based on literature review methodology, while the remaining 8 (11.6%) were theoretical papers.

S/No.	Method used	No. of Studies
1	Qualitative	30
2	Quantitative	17
3	Mixed method	10
4	Literature review method	4
5	Theoretical papers	8
Total		69

Figure 5: Number of Articles by Method Used

To understand the spread of the literature reviewed across countries, we identified those across developed and developing countries that have published articles on the phenomenon under study. In the developed countries, the United States of America has the highest percentage with 24.64%, followed by China with 10.14%, and Australia with 7.25%. While in developing countries, Canada has the highest rate of 4.35%, followed by South Africa with 2.90%. Based on the reviewed literature, no study was conducted on this phenomenon under investigation in Nigerian higher educational institutions as indicated in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6: Study Distribution by Country

The Overarching theme: Toward theory development

Overarching theme: Epistemological Access Investigating epistemological access is phenomenal; it has attracted many scholars over the years ((Du-Plooy & Zilindile, 2014; Lockett, 2019; Morrow, 1994; Morrow, 2009; Willey, 2007). Epistemological access is an access that is bestowed upon students with the purpose of gaining mastery of the subject area in their disciplinary domain (Lockett, 2019; Morrow, 2009). Consequently, epistemological access requires a process theorization approach, to ensure gaining the disciplinary knowledge of the domain area and in-dept understanding (Fagan, 2020; Gamede,

2006; Luckett, 2019; Maniram, 2018; Mistri, 2016; Myers, 2019; Ongito, 2012; Venter, 2020). Some studies aligned with this view, though with varied perspectives. Some consider epistemological access which was first used by Willey (2007), a South African scholar, who problematized access to higher education. He used the term to describe two dimensions of access to higher education, being institutional (formal access) and access to knowledge, which he believes institutions distribute (epistemological access).

However, finding from this study corroborates with the second perspective (i.e., access to knowledge which morrow believes institution distribute 'epistemological access'). Within this study epistemological access is pinned at meaningful access to knowledge, when learning is structured in a manner which ensures learners develop coherent ways of engaging with digital technologies and understanding different learning areas (Pendlebury, 2009, p. 24-25). This access, therefore, extends beyond mere physical access to include the ways in which learners are provided with quality education. This is because our outcome describes activity-based events as characterized gaining the right knowledge of the disciplinary domain, which is continuously influence by mechanisms of people, structures, and cultures.

RQ1. *How are the educational affordances of digital technologies for gaining epistemological access among marginalized groups contextualized in higher institutions in sub-Saharan African universities?*

Thus, to answer RQ1 stated in the introduction, we cover extent literature to discover events that characterized epistemological access. Consequently, we identified three key themes from the synthesized literature. The themes include educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities. We discuss these themes by starting with the first theme, educational technological affordances, as detailed below.

Theme One: educational technological affordances

The term 'affordances' (Gibson, 1977), often known as action possibilities, refers to the relationship between the perceived and actual qualities of digital technology. Thus, the way technology provides opportunities for learning is frequently influenced by the underlying pedagogy. Affordances and constraints, relates to how digital technologies might potentially be deployed and used (Major & Warwick, 2019). Educational technological affordance is one of the key existing entities that is fundamental to epistemological access in the current trends (Bower, 2008; Major et al., 2022; Major et al., 2018). This theme, 'educational technological affordances,' explores the concepts that describe the relevancy of education using ICT-related facilities. The concepts of educational technological affordances include engaging in productive processes, engaging in co-construction, monitoring and regulation, (Jeong & Hmelo-Silver, 2016), representation of content (Major & Warwick, 2019), engaging in productive processes, engaging in co-construction, monitoring and regulation (Jeong & Hmelo-Silver, 2016), browsing, selection, supportive/challenging, assistive memory, control (Cook et al., 2019), and usability (Shin, 2021). Educational technological affordance guide towards gaining access to education in higher education institutions. Thus, affordance has been used in other fields like human-computer interaction (Turner, 2005), information systems (Norman, 1999; Seidel et al., 2013; Volkoff & Strong, 2017), computer science, decision support systems (Leifler, 2011), artificial intelligence and robotics (Lemaignan et al., 2017), engineering (Maier & Fadel, 2001), and education (Bower, 2008). Although, technology affordance is described in a variety of ways in the literature. Wijekummar et al. (2006) defined affordances as the interactions between users and tools in ways that influence and guide collaborations (Carter et al., 1999). Gaver (1991) explored affordances as the strengths and weaknesses of technology that could be offered to users. Graves (2007) looked at technological affordances to bridge the gap between determinist and social constructivist approaches. That description is different from that of Mao (2014), who described technological affordances as the technological features or functions that extend learning and perceptual capabilities, which might be economic, social, cognitive, or affective. In this context, therefore, affordance is described as the action possibilities that an object gives to user, given the competency, skills, or expertise of the user. Affordance thus emerges from the interaction of technology and user characteristics (Bobsin et al., 2019). However, affordances are not always indefinable a priori, although they are easily observable when the technology application context is understood. Technology affordances influence students' interactions with technology and how they learn a subject using technology (Burlamaqui & Dong, 2017). Being rooted in the action potential offered by objects (i.e., technology) (Paul M Leonardi, 2013; Majchrzak & Markus, 2012), it may still be actualized or even perceived regardless of the context.

Digital technology has become increasingly integrated into classrooms to support and enrich student learning, (Dillenbourg & Hong, 2008; Lahiri & Moseley, 2015; Zaka, 2012) particularly in fostering self-directed and collaborative learning experiences. This approach aligns with the current trend in educational planning to prioritize self-directed learning with the aid of technology (Collins & Halverson, 2010; Jonassen & Hung, 2008). Teachers are encouraged to leverage digital tools and collaborative methods to facilitate dialogic interactions among students in technology-supported classrooms. These interactions not only enhance knowledge exchange but also empower students to actively engage with course materials and peers, thereby fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Through digital technology, students can work together seamlessly,

communicate effectively, and access resources efficiently, ultimately promoting a more dynamic and interactive educational experience (Maher, 2012). Therefore, we state the following proposition:

P1: Educational technological affordances will guide to gain epistemological access in sub-Saharan Africa.

Theme Two: learning context

The discussed theme focuses on the impact of digital technology on the learning context, emphasizing its role in enhancing learner autonomy (Al-Ani, 2013; Payton & Kvasny, 2016), inclusion, participation, classroom atmosphere, motivation, engagement, and interpersonal relationships (Al-Ani, 2013; Asamoah & Andoh-Baidoo, 2018). Studies show that digital technologies can empower students to take greater ownership of their learning by facilitating cooperative decision-making and self-monitoring of progress (Maher, 2012). Moreover, digital tools encourage learner inclusion and participation through collaborative group interactions, democratic decision-making, and increased intrinsic interest in learning apps (Ilomäki & Lakkala, 2018). Additionally, digital technology contributes to a positive teaching environment by fostering a sense of community, solidarity, and collaboration among students, as well as promoting increased interaction and open questioning by teachers. Furthermore, it enhances interpersonal relationships, particularly between teachers and students, and among students themselves, when the quality of interactions improves. Lastly, digital technology boosts learner motivation and engagement by stimulating curiosity, providing enjoyable learning experiences, and offering relevant and applicable tools.

In dialogical classroom interaction for teaching and learning, when digital technology is used to perform certain responsibilities like problem solving, information management, skills acquisition, and collaboration with respect to effectiveness, efficiency, and ethics, competence is very important and it is referred to as a group of skills, knowledge, and attitudes (Ferrari, 2012), that can be applied by a group of individuals. Therefore, learning context is critical in providing education to students in the educational context.

P6: In higher education institutions, learning context will guide sub-Saharan African countries in gaining epistemological access.

Theme Three: dialogic activities

This section addresses four major sub-themes related to the ‘dialogic activities’ theme. Studies (Brown & Dillard, 2015; Li et al., 2022; Major & Warwick, 2019; Smeda et al., 2014; Tiven et al., 2018) examine how digital technology can improve dialogic engagement by increasing exposure to diverse viewpoints. This includes providing children with frequent opportunities to recognize that their peers hold opposing viewpoints. For example, a study reporting an online asynchronous discussion making alternative views of a science topic more memorable by modeling the process of distinguishing ideas (Place, 2019). Furthermore, digital technology such as micro-blogging tool can enable students with minimal background knowledge to tap into a pool of other students’ viewpoints, example, readers or ‘followers’ can access and engage with a variety of ‘contributions’ given by others (Singleton, 2016). Several research studies (Bo et al., 2018; Bower, 2008; Charitonos, 2015; Davidsen & Vanderlinde, 2016) address the issue of considering the perspectives of others. For example, prompting students to consider the ‘audience’ and explain, comment, or contribute to an online forum where the process of externalizing ideas pushes students to carry out deeper explanations (Seethamraju, 2014).

The section illustrates how digital technology supports knowledge co-construction and metacognitive learning among students. It discusses various methods such as collaborative production of digital artifacts like Talkwall, which fosters shared cognition and collective evaluation. Additionally, it highlights the role of technology-mediated debate and video-stimulated reflective discussions in promoting metacognition. Furthermore, it explores how dialogue, facilitated by digital platforms, aids in understanding peers and provides technical support. Teachers play a crucial role in scaffolding comprehension through dialogue and technology, exemplified by tools like Talkwall and strategies like establishing ground rules for talk. Overall, this highlights the importance of technology-enhanced dialogue in facilitating learning and collaboration among students.

P3: Synergy between educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities will be more effective in gaining epistemological access in higher education institutions in sub-Saharan Africa.

RQ2. What challenges may implicate gaining epistemological access in a quest to use digital technology for dialogic interaction in higher education institutions in sub-Saharan Africa?

In this section, we describe the findings of the theme synthesis in response to RQ2. Following a literature synthesis process, two high-level themes were identified, which linked to the challenges of using digital technology to help acquire epistemological access from the standpoint of the users, i. students; ii. teachers. As with the theme synthesis for RQ1, these are broad categories, and several research studies identify multiple issues.

RQ2 theme one – challenges facing students

The section discusses challenges that students may encounter when engaging in dialogic interaction with digital technologies. It explores factors such as students’ technical skills, knowledge, and access to technology, impacting their ability

to effectively utilize digital tools for learning. Challenges include unfamiliarity with tools, lack of access to necessary devices or applications, spelling errors affecting message comprehension, and limitations in reading and writing abilities hindering participation. Additionally, unequal access to technology and poor engagement rates pose barriers to learner inclusion and engagement. Issues such as varying prior experiences and expectations among students complicate classroom dialogic interactions. The text emphasizes the importance of active participation and synchronous peer conversations to maintain focused discussions, highlighting the need for addressing these challenges to facilitate effective interaction with digital technologies in education.

It highlights the diverse perceptions students hold regarding the value of technology in learning, often focusing on the superficial qualities of ICT tools. Challenges arise from students' varying levels of interaction with digital technologies, with some preferring individual work over interactive activities. Additionally, technology use can lead to distractions or frustrations, such as physical features of digital tools or administrative tasks like remembering usernames and passwords. Understanding these challenges is crucial for teachers to effectively integrate digital technologies into classroom dialogic interaction, particularly in regions like sub-Saharan Africa, to ensure equitable access to learning opportunities for all students.

RQ2 theme two – challenges facing teachers

This section addresses the potential challenges that teachers may face. The section deals with issues related to classroom management of learning.

Studies addresses pedagogical challenges faced by teachers regarding the use of digital technologies in classroom dialogic interaction. Central concerns include the quality of teacher questioning and student discussion. Teachers often employ closed questioning on learning management systems (e.g., Alexander et al., 2017; Lyle, 2008), while opportunities for deeper engagement through uptake questions are limited. Additionally, challenges arise when attempting to foster a new learning culture, including addressing instructors' belief systems and navigating systemic school cultures and curricular frameworks. Teachers must establish supportive social infrastructures for inquiry-based learning, despite the associated challenges. Broad pedagogical challenges include the need for shifts in pedagogical practices and providing professional support for integrating digital technology into teaching. These challenges encompass instructional design issues and ensuring sustained student engagement with digital tools over time. Addressing these challenges is crucial for effectively integrating digital technologies into teaching practices. The instructional design challenges, such as the possibility of using the same function of a technology to support both dialogic and more traditional didactic strategies (Johnson et al., 2016), as well as ensuring that student use of a tool does not change over time (Major & Warwick, 2019; Mohammed, 2019).

Challenges can occur because of the increasing pace of technology-based education (i.e., EduTech). For example, given the rapid pace of asynchronous group discussion, teachers' attempts to guide and supervise the topic may easily be disregarded (Koch, 2017). There are other effects on instructors' time management, such as the additional pre-planning required when using the learning management system (Fathema & Akanda, 2020; Zafarullah et al., 2016) and the time-consuming nature of following threaded discussions in CSCL environments (J.-T. Lee et al., 2014). Teachers also expressed their concerns about new behavior management challenges. Students, for example, may get disinterested when interacting with learning management system (Cicekci & Sadik, 2019; Mohammadi et al., 2021), whilst some teachers may be challenged by the manner in which students express themselves when conversing digitally, including their use of slang and inappropriate language (Åberg & Waller, 2012).

The challenges resulting from teachers' technical skills are a penultimate feature of included studies. It was reported in some studies (Buabeng-Andoh, 2012; Guerriero, 2014; Lodge et al., 2018) that, teachers should have a specific level of technical skills when employing digital technology to enhance dialogic interaction. This, for example, will allow teachers to become fully acquainted with the benefits of a technology's features (Cardullo & Wilson, 2015). It is also important having the necessary access to existing high digital resources to support teachers to deploy technology effectively in the classroom (Bower, 2008; Cardullo & Wilson, 2015; Cook et al., 2019; Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015; Major et al., 2022).

Theorizing constructs of digital technology affordance for epistemological access

Drawing from the conceptual themes extracted from literature reviewed, we answered the research question one and two, by theorizing a framework as shown in **Figure 7**. The framework consists of three domains, i. T1-T2 cultural conditioning and structural conditioning; ii. T2-T3 social/socio-cultural interactions; and iii. T3-T4 structural/cultural elaboration. The framework highlights the identified events as the answer to research question one in the first and second segments (i.e., T1-T2, & T2-T3). Further, the third segment (i.e., T3-T4) of the framework provide answer to research question two.

At T1-T2 of the framework, the students are coming into the university as freshers. Similarly, the artifactual structures (socio-technical structures) are all in place in the University for Dialogic Classroom Interaction. By contrast, it is recognized that socio-technical structures pre-date students' enrolment into the university because the students meet those structures at the

time of admission. In a quest to use digital technologies provided at higher educational institutions, there are affordances that a designer integrates into the EduTech. These are structural, instructive, and functional affordances. According to Ditzler et al. (2018, p. 22), “structural affordances are the object material features, properties, or capabilities of a tool.” In this context, the EduTech are design for dialogic classroom interaction that students can interact with. Meanwhile, EduTech, in this case, have been in place before students enrolled into a university. The features and affordances of EduTech create objective context for students, with structural, instructive, and functional affordances fed into time period T2-T3, this serve as the first theme discovered in this study (i.e., **Educational Technological Affordances**). When these affordances are fed into time period T2-T3, we may now analyze students-teacher interacting with the digital technologies (example, learning management systems, Talkwall, social media, etc.) in a particular environment (i.e., university) referred to as **Learning Contexts**. During the interaction, the mechanisms triggering the interaction process, when it comes to people emergent properties (PEP), are reflexivity, manipulation, exploration, and sense-making. For the structural emergent properties (SEP), it comprises of IT affordances, institution, political, and legal structures that trigger the interaction process. While the cultural system of a particular university are the cultural emergent properties (CEP) that trigger the interaction between students-teachers, which is dialogic interaction and possibly acquiring a laptop over the time period T2-T3 as the last theme identified in this study (i.e., **Dialogic Activities**). As students-teachers involve in constant interaction with digital technologies at time period T2-T3, while user enactment of affordance processes is going on, ‘Epistemological Access’ can be gained as the overarching theme (i.e., **phenomenon**). When the epistemological access is gained in higher education institution using digital technologies, there will be students’ change, change in the technology and change in the culture at time period T3-T4. Meanwhile, they have undergone changes and metamorphose into something else, a transformational affordance has been achieved. Archer referred to structural elaboration ‘morphogenesis’ (Archer, 1995). But if the change has not occurred (i.e., morphostasis) where students, teachers face some challenges of either digital technology, institutional, political/legal challenges, epistemological access has not been achieved, as such T3-T4 will now become T1.

Figure 7: Theoretical framework of educational technology affordances and epistemological access. Source (Authors)

Discussion

A systematic literature review was conducted, analyzing 69 studies to address two research questions regarding the use of digital technologies for education in sub-Saharan African universities. The questions focused on the affordances of digital technologies for marginalized groups’ epistemological access and the challenges hindering such access. The goal was to map peer-reviewed studies from 2012 to 2022 and assess the potential and limitations of digital technology in improving classroom interaction. The discussion outlines issues identified in existing research and extends to thematic and sub-thematic considerations, suggesting avenues for further study stimulated by the systematic review.

The study further discusses the search process and findings of a systematic review on digital technology in education, highlighting several key points. Firstly, it notes a prevalence of studies in information systems education, possibly due to a

focus on argumentation and reasoning in scientific inquiry. Secondly, there is a scarcity of studies from sub-Saharan Africa, potentially influenced by the narrow range of technologies studied, leading to a bias towards regions with higher adoption rates. Additionally, many digital technologies used in education were initially developed for other purposes. Overall, the studies identified vary in their aims, scope, and theoretical framing, but many are influenced by sociocultural perspectives emphasizing the role of digital technologies in individuals' relationships with their surroundings.

The study delves into the interdependence of learning components, emphasizing the sociocultural viewpoint that considers how tools, both mental and material, are used in human activity to generate knowledge. It notes that while new digital technologies may not inherently improve learning, they can significantly impact engagement. The thematic synthesis identifies themes around digital technology affordance and dialogic interactions, highlighting their role in gaining epistemological access. The concept of affordance is explored, emphasizing the importance of aligning technology use with educational goals. The study concludes by advocating for collaboration between experts, designers, teachers, researchers, and students to fully explore the potential of digital technology in enhancing learning.

Conclusion

The study aimed to understand how marginalized groups can access epistemological knowledge in higher institutions, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. This was achieved through two main approaches: conducting a systematic literature review on digital technologies and developing a theoretical framework. The review highlighted a gap in existing research, which often focused on technology or students separately, rather than their integrated interactions for achieving epistemological access. The synthesized theoretical framework offers an integrated perspective on how structural and cultural systems of students and digital technology can interact to facilitate epistemic access. Additionally, it addresses gaps such as the influence of e-learning management systems on faculty during dialogic interaction. The framework not only provides new research avenues in the information systems domain but also serves as inspiration for future empirical testing in higher educational institutions globally.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, higher institutions should develop and implement an integrated digital learning platform that consolidates user educational resources, digital academic communication, research and innovation, remote learning, virtual engagement, digital libraries, and inclusive digital education. This platform should be user-friendly, ensuring seamless navigation and accessibility for underprivileged students. Universities should invest in user-centric design principles to enhance the usability of digital technologies for underprivileged students. Prioritize user friendly design, optimizing outcomes, and adaptive flexibility in the development and deployment of digital tools. Solicit regular feedback from underprivileged students to iteratively improve the user interface and overall usability of digital platforms. Universities in Nigeria should implement educational strategies that capitalize on the identified transformational changes associated with underprivileged students' interaction with digital technologies. Foster personalized learning experiences, encourage global collaboration and connectivity, integrate holistic learning and skills development, and promote inclusivity and global education. This may involve the development of tailored programs, mentorship opportunities, and collaborative projects that leverage digital technologies.

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